

Fiber Optic Loop Based Integrated RF-Photonic System for Analog Signal Processing

Weimin Zhou and Michael R. Stead

U.S. Army Research Laboratory, 2800 Powder Mill Road, Adelphi MD20783
weimin.zhou.civ@mail.mil, Michael.r.stead.civ@mail.mil

Abstract: We developed a fiber-optic-loop based system that replicates a single RF input pulse to produce thousands of signal pairs in time domain for auto-correlation processing. A new noise redistribution feature improved the system signal-to-noise performance which allows high resolution spectral analysis for a single signal-pulse.

Summary

We have developed a new type of RF-Photonic, analogue, time-correlation signal processor [1-3]. The goal is to provide an RF frequency spectrum from a single, short, input “pulse” signal. Conventional signal detection and processing techniques are limited by the digital processor’s bit-rate which cannot adequately resolve frequency information from a very short duration signal. In our RF-photonic analogue signal correlation processor, a laser carrier is modulated by the RF microwave input signal pulse $f(\omega_{RF}t)$ which is sent into a fiber-optic-recirculation-loop circuit so the “live” RF signal can circulate in the loop over a long time. Previously, we had achieved the requisite stepped time delay, Δt , by using a dual optical path pulse replicating loop with two optical carriers with a small length difference between paths for each round trip loop circulation. [1] However, there are two sidebands created by the RF modulation of a single carrier which travel in the fiber with different group velocities due to the dispersion effect in the fiber. This means a single optical carrier may generate a train of recirculated pulse pairs with an increasing time delay, $n\Delta t$ (n =pulse replica number), between them, which can be mixed to perform an auto-correlation. [2-3] By digitizing the base-band correlation output signal from our RF-Photonic signal time-correlation processor and performing a fast Fourier transform (FFT) from $n\Delta t$ to ω_{RF} space, we can obtain the frequency spectrum for the input RF pulse. Here, n is the number of circulation in the optical loop, therefore, in order to obtain fine spectral resolution, we want to make as many circulations as possible. However, even though the signal loss in the optical fiber is small, tapping the signal from the 2x2 coupler for each loop circulation still causes signal loss which needs to be compensated by an Er doped fiber amplifier (EDFA) to maintain the optical pulse intensity. The EDFA introduces optical noise into the system which will be re-amplified many times. As consequence, after one or two hundreds circulations, the signal to noise ratio becomes negligible. Therefore increasing the number of replicas with reasonable RF signal to noise ratio is the major challenge for this analogue correlation loop technology. In this work, we present an improved RF-photonic fiber-recirculation-loop auto-correlation circuit architecture. This architecture distributes a single input signal in the time domain and allows the signal-to-noise ratio decay to be redistributed periodically over thousands of pulse replicas produced by the loop circuit, therefore producing thousands of correlation terms for a high resolution spectral analysis of the input pulse signal.

The innovation of the reinjecting recirculation-loop circuit is that no EDFA will be placed in the recirculating loop. Instead, the EDFA is placed in a much longer (24x longer) reinjecting loop which is used to store the signal pulse and maintain its amplitude level. Only a small portion (5%) of the input pulse is sent to the recirculating loop with the rest diverted to the reinjecting loop. It generates a train of pulse replicas which decay in amplitude, but it does not generate additional EDFA noise with each transit. After 24 replicas are created, the signal is too small to be useful, and another full power pulse is tapped out of the reinjecting loop and into the recirculating loop, which creates another 24 replicas, synchronized to follow in step with the previous 24, and so on. This means the EDFA augments the noise level only once for every 24 recirculations instead of every time. This allows for the creation of over 20 times more pulse replica pairs.

The RF modulation applied to the optical carrier creates two sidebands separated from the carrier by, ω_{RF} ($=2\pi f_{RF}$). These sidebands travel through fiber at different speeds due to dispersion, creating a relative time delay, “ Δt ”, for each loop round trip. Using Corning smf-28e optical fiber at 1.5 μ m wavelength, the dispersion relation is quite linear for the RF frequencies studied, therefore we can express: $\Delta t = \omega_{RF}\tau_0$, where τ_0 is a constant.[2,3] Therefore, this loop circuit creates, from a single input pulse, a train of pulses with RF sidebands pairs having Δt , $2\Delta t$, $3\Delta t$... $n\Delta t$, delays

between the sidebands. The RF signal carried by both sidebands is extracted from the optical carrier with a high-speed photodetector, and sent to a RF mixing square-law detector. For each replicated pulse, the output from the square-law detector is the correlation coefficient between a pair of RF signals: $E(\omega_{RF} t) \times E[\omega_{RF} (t-k\Delta t)]$, where k represent k^{th} replica. With a low pass filter, the baseband correlation coefficient, $A \exp(ik\omega_{RF} \Delta t)$ is determined, which can be expressed by $A \exp(ik\omega_{RF}^2 \tau_0)$, therefore, one can perform simple Fourier transformation between time space “ $k\tau_0$ ” and frequency squared, ω_{RF}^2 , space to obtain the frequency spectrum for the input RF signal.

We have conducted a series of experiments by sending a single RF pulse (about $3\mu\text{s}$ duration) to the input port (the optical modulator) of our recirculation-loop-circuit system to perform the analog signal auto-correlation and FFT. The RF pulse signal is generated by a CW RF signal source with a single tone frequency. Several frequency from 5GHz to 40GHz were tested. The recirculation-loop-circuit produced the baseband data represented by $A \exp(ik\omega_{RF}^2 \tau_0)$. However, due to the periodic exponential optical pulse amplitude decay from our unamplified loop, the amplitude, A , is also a function of $k\tau_0$ with a periodic change which is shown in Fig.1. In our experimental set up, the period for k is 24, and we were able to obtain a total 4096 replica pulses. This periodic change will produce a series of “spurious” frequencies after the Fourier transform. In order to eliminate the spurs, we need to correct the artificial exponential decay behaviors on A by a normalization process. We have used a step-gain amplifier* on the base-band correlation output signal to do a partial analog normalization process. Using these data, we can have a better determination of the noise floor change in each period which allows us to perform additional digital normalization calculations to farther reduce the spurs in the frequency spectrum after the FFT. Figure 2 shows one experimental result of the RF spectrum data obtained by the FFT of A). raw correlation data from a 35GHz, short input RF signal pulse ($3\mu\text{s}$) without the normalization process, B). normalized correlation data with both analog and digital normalization processes for the same input signal. Significant spur reduction has been achieved.

Fig.1. Time-domain raw data of 4096 pulse replica generated by the recirculation-loop circuit.

Fig.2. RF spectrum obtained from FFT of the time-correlation data before (top) and after (bottom) the normalization process.

In conclusion, we have demonstrated a new reinjecting fiber-optic-recirculation-loop circuit that can distribute a single input RF-signal pulse in time to produce more than 4096 replicas with reasonable signal-to-noise-ratios to perform auto-correlation which can provide a high-resolution RF spectrum with 50GHz bandwidth for a single input signal pulse having $3\mu\text{s}$ pulse duration. This RF-photonics time-domain auto-correlator has potential provide high frequency spectrum analysis for a single ultra-short signal pulse with reasonable resolution and quick signal processing time.

References:

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